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**THE PROFITABILITY THRESHOLD IN PRICING POLICY
UNDER CONDITIONS OF UNCERTAINTY
(Preliminary Version)**

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ABSTRACT

This paper has as its aim consideration of the possibility of restructuring the profitability threshold model so as to allow its use as an auxiliary tool in pricing policy decisions.

With this in mind, in the light of the limitations imposed by the traditional approach to profitability thresholds, it proposes the application of fuzzy set theory so as to develop a "fuzzy threshold of profitability". This would incorporate variables which are of significance for decisions on pricing, such as potential demand, the cost of getting a new product into the market, and the costs of sales and distribution, together with possible interconnections between these variables.

KEY WORDS : Pricing Policy, Fuzzy Numbers, Decision Making in Uncertainty ; Profitability Threshold Model, Cost-Volume-Profit Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Establishment of the sales price of a product is one of the fundamental management decisions. Management accounting, which is intended to be the source of valid information for decision making, must provide data to aid in the fixing of optional and/or satisfactory prices. It must also supply information for analysis of the implications that these prices have for the overall objectives of the enterprise.

The models habitually used in deciding prices have been based either on marginal costs or on accounting costs models, from which have been derived intermediate models examining the behaviour of the variables involved. Nevertheless, these models have various shortcomings, particularly in connection with the starting hypotheses which they adopt. One of these restrictions lies in the difficulty of knowing with certainty what future situations will be. The solution adopted by these models is to assimilate the future to past situations and to extrapolate from past to future behaviour on the basis of statistical inferencing (probability).

Such an approach is challenged by this paper, since it is a long way from the changeability and complexity which characterise the present day economic environment, where information about the variables in question is only imprecise or uncertain.

Moreover, traditional models approach the question of fixing prices without including significant variables affecting it. This paper raises the interesting possibility of the inclusion in the case under consideration of information on relevant variables. These might be the potential demand (and thus the likely market share), the cost of producing the goods, the cost of breaking into the market (advertising, promotional campaigns, and so forth), the cost of sales and distribution and the like, these also being variables about which there is no precise information.

In the light of the above, this paper suggests the possibility of restructuring the cost-volume-profit model as a management accounting tool, with the aim of extending its usefulness to problems of price analysis, while attempting to avoid the shortcomings mentioned above.

Thus, the next section will consider the application of fuzzy set theory to the cost-volume-profit model, leading to the establishment of a fuzzy threshold of profitability. This will permit its use when the information available is precise.

Once the fuzzy threshold of profitability is established, a further section, the third, will attempt to round out this model by incorporating variables which the traditional model excluded, such as potential demand. This will allow an analysis of how sensitive possible prices are to the remaining associated variables, and to the overall objectives of the firm.

A fourth and final section will offer a practical application of this model to a typical problem, in this specific instance consideration of the effects of the price on the launch of a new product.

II. APPLICATION OF THE THEORY OF FUZZY SETS TO THE COST-VOLUME-PROFIT MODEL: THE FUZZY THRESHOLD OF PROFITABILITY

To aid in the making of management decisions, especially profit planning, where it is necessary to make operational judgements involving fixing a price for goods or services, it is of considerable interest to discover the relationships between costs, production volume and profits.

Thus, the cost-volume-profit model is one of the most heavily used tools aiding in the making of such decisions. This is because it offers a simple and easy way of analysing the variations that possible modifications of one of the variables involved would bring about in the others.

The relationship between profit, income and costs of an economic unit is represented by the following equation:

$$B = X \times P_v - [X \times CV_u + CF] \quad (1)$$

where :

- X : Product units
- P_v : Unit sale price
- CF: Fixed costs
- CV_u : Variable costs
- I: Income
- CVT: Total Variable costs
- B: Profit

and, thus:

$$P_v \times X = CV_u \times X + CF + B \quad [2]$$

that is to say, sales equal the sum of fixed costs, variable costs and profit.

The fundamental aim of the point of balance model is to determine at what level of production the firm reaches a balance between costs and income, thus having neither profits nor losses. This occurs when the income generated by the firm's products is enough to cover all fixed and variable costs arising in the period considered. In this case, making $B = 0$, the following equation can be obtained from expression [2]:

$$X = \frac{CF}{P_v - CV_u} \quad [3]$$

where the denominator ($P_v - CV_u$) is known as the contributory margin. Its economic significance is that this is the contribution that each unit made and sold makes towards covering fixed costs, and, when once these are totally covered, that is once the profitability threshold has been reached, the contribution to profits by each unit.

As shown above, the acceptance of the cost-volume-profit model as an operational tool in taking decisions is initially an outcome of its ease of use in expressing the behaviour of costs and income and their relation both with the volume of production and with profits. However, it is traditionally brought into play on the basis of a series of hypotheses adopted to give it simplicity and flexibility in use [HORNGREN, 1984, p. 52]. Among these, the fact that it is applied to a deterministic situation stands out as crucial.

This means that the validity of the model is restricted exclusively to those cases in which the values of component variables of the model are known. It is thus valid only for

decision making in circumstances of certainty or situations where the event under consideration recurs in space and/or in time, allowing measurements and calculation of the probability of its occurrence. This is done by assigning it a random variable and finding out its distribution, so that statistical techniques can be employed [JAEDICKE and ROBICHEK, 1964; FERRARA, HAYYA and NACHMAN, 1972; LIAO, 1975; ADAR, BARNEA and LEV, 1977].

However, the conclusions drawn from the so-called "random model" are similarly of no use when the model is applied to shifting circumstances. This is particularly true in those referring to the future where past data are not so relevant to the decision making process, and where the information available is subjective, imprecise and uncertain.

Thus, to apply the model in situations which are neither deterministic nor random, it would be desirable to restructure it. This led to the proposal that fuzzy set theory should be applied to it.

Vague or fuzzy numbers were created so as to reflect the vagueness of human perception and so the notion of assumptions. The theory of fuzzy sets, the branch of mathematics dealing with the treatment of what is subjected and what is uncertain, represents an attempt to grasp a phenomenon as it occurs in real life, and to handle it without trying to deform it into something precise and certain [ZADEH, 1965].

To apply cost-volume-profit analysis to a great majority of situations, it would be necessary to work with forecast data, derived from subjective estimates or expert judgements. This is particularly so if firm information relating to the future is not available and it is not a case of repeated or iterative situations that can be measured. So, if the information to hand is uncertain, it must be handled with mathematical tools that permit treatment of uncertainty. This suggests the application of fuzzy set theory to the area [MENDAÑA CUERVO, 1995].

As a consequence, the calculation of a point of balance in conditions of uncertainty would cease to involve a "point" and becomes a "range" or set of possible values. There would also be a difference from the procedure in conditions of certainty in respect both of the way of gathering information, rendered much more feasible, and the manner in which it is treated. Specifically, in this paper, for illustrative purpose, the information available has been assumed to be in the form of confidence triplets (although the model can be adapted to other forms of uncertain expression). Thus, by simple application of the arithmetic of fuzzy mathematics, and using the same symbols as previously:

$$\begin{aligned} & [X_1, X_2, X_3] \\ & [P_{v1}, P_{v2}, P_{v3}] \\ & [CF_1, CF_2, CF_3] \\ & [CV_{u1}, CV_{u2}, CV_{u3}] \end{aligned}$$

The amount at which the threshold of profitability is reached (this no longer being a point), will then be given by the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} [X_1, X_2, X_3] &= \frac{[CF_1, CF_2, CF_3]}{[P_{v1}, P_{v2}, P_{v3}] - [CV_{u1}, CV_{u2}, CV_{u3}]} = \\ &= \frac{[CF_1, CF_2, CF_3]}{[P_{v1} - CV_{u3}, P_{v2} - CV_{u2}, P_{v3} - CV_{u1}]} \quad [4] \end{aligned}$$

By simplification in [4], for the case of R^+ , the fuzzy threshold of profitability would be shown by:

$$[\hat{X}] = [X_1, X_2, X_3] = \left[\frac{CF_1}{P_{v3} - CV_{u1}}, \frac{CF_2}{P_{v2} - CV_{u2}}, \frac{CF_3}{P_{v1} - CV_{u3}} \right] \quad [5]$$

Obviously, as a consequence of working with confidence triplets, the result will be expressed in the same terms, and the graphic representation of it will be as in Figure 1.

Figure1

So, the profitability threshold calculated in this way has, for the problem data, the range of possibilities of reaching the threshold, as a function of the level of assumption specified, such that it will never be below X_1 nor above X_3 , with the highest possibility of it being reached at X_2 .

III. THE FUZZY THRESHOLD OF PROFITABILITY MODEL APPLIED TO PRICE ANALYSIS

When applied to the problem of fixing prices, the fuzzy threshold of profitability proposed in the previous section is just as able as the traditional model to determine how possible changes in price will affect the result. However, with this model it is feasible to work with all the uncertainty arising from the variables used, so that when applied to problems relating to the future all the outcomes that might occur can be included.

Nevertheless, the main advantage offered by this model as compared with the traditional one is its ability to take into account variables affecting pricing which the classic model does not consider. This rounds out the analysis of the impact of pricing on results.

In this section the operation of fuzzy thresholds of profitability in fixing prices will first be explained. Thereafter, the model will be expanded by incorporation of aspects such as market share, the effects of advertising and promotional costs, and the like.

It is clear that variations in price directly affect the contributory margin, and thus the denominator of the expression defining the fuzzy threshold of profitability. Moreover, it is obvious that for changes in the sales prices there is a lower limit which is the same as the unit variable cost, assuming there are no fixed costs. This is because a price set below this level would cause each unit sold to generate losses to the amount of the difference between the price set and the limit. If there are fixed costs or costs relating to the establishment of a minimum profitable capacity, the lower limit for the unit sales price must cover both variable costs and the required amount for the unit contribution to covering these other costs.

In any case, an increase in the sales price will lower the volume at which balance is reached. This means that there will be a leftwards movement of the triplet defining the threshold in relation to its initial values. There will also be a decrease in the spread of the new threshold, as long as the variation is proportional, so that:

$$\begin{aligned} & [P_{v1}, P_{v2}, P_{v3}] \\ & [k + P_{v1}, k + P_{v2}, k + P_{v3}] \end{aligned}$$

where k is a constant. Decreases in the sales price will have the opposite effect, as is shown by Figure 2.

Figure 2

It seems clear that these results are similar to those arising from decreases or increases in the unit variable cost. This is because of the inverse effect that such changes have upon the contributory margin and the influence of this on the threshold of profitability.

Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis of the model proposed can be rounded out by investigation of the influence of a number of variables related to it. One such would be the volume of sales, which has no influence over the number of units at which the threshold is reached, but, when it is reached, does become a variable representing the possible profits to be made.

In accordance with formula [5], and noting the volume of sales as $[Z_1, Z_2, Z_3]$, the profit will be shown by the expression:

$$B^{\circ} = [[Z_1, Z_2, Z_3] - [X_1, X_2, X_3]] \times [P_{v1}, P_{v2}, P_{v3}] \quad [8]$$

This allows an analysis of the business potential for the initial state, without the shortcoming of assuming infinite sales volumes which lead to the appearance in the analysis of unlimited profits.

Thus, cost-volume-profit analysis allows variations in profits to be traced as a function of values assigned, achieved at different volumes of production and sales, at different prices and with varying levels of fixed costs and behaviours of variable costs. This renders feasible not merely study of the effects brought about by change in one of these variables individually, but also by reason of the interconnections between them.

However, making modifications in different variables and analysing their effects on profits requires the incorporation into the model of further variables which act as a restriction upon profits. Among these, one of the principal limitations on the volume of sales, and thus on profits, is market share.

The traditional model of the point of balance allows for unlimited profits from increases in the number of units sold, since information about market share, because it refers to the future, is not known with certainty. On the other hand, with the fuzzy threshold of profitability model, it is feasible to request experts to assign a value for market share, as for all the other variables. With information expressed in the form of triplets as before, this would be shown by an expression such as the following:

Market Share : [CM₁, CM₂, CM₃]

This variable in its turn will be influenced by some of the variables involved in the model, because pricing changes will not merely affect the threshold of profitability and the possibility of profits, but will also have an immediate effect upon market share. For example, it seems clear that increases in the unit sales price will be inversely reflected in the market share, and vice versa. The extent of this effect may be factored into the model by simply requesting experts to estimate a value for it.

Similarly, and once again on the basis of information supplied by experts, it is possible to analyse the influence of variables such as capacity of resources, marketing policy and so forth. This would indicate any correlations between these and other variables in the model, as will be demonstrated in the example in the next section.

IV. AN EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION IN PRACTICE

From what has been said so far, the feasibility and validity of the model for various decision making situations seen in terms of the variables affecting them may be deduced. What is more, the model can remedy some of the deficiencies of use under conditions of certainty. To aid in checking the model, a practical example will now be given. This will be representative of various alternative analyses and will offer a comparative study of each of the outcomes. The information on economic data given by experts will be expressed as confidence triplets and treated using software developed by the authoress of this paper.

For this purpose, let it be supposed that a health company is interested in setting up in the city of Leon a clinic for the ophthalmological treatment of cataracts, since according to statistical data approximately 3,000 people each year receive treatment for this condition in the form of a two-day stay in hospital at a cost of 15,000 pesetas per case. On the other hand, use of the procedure which it is proposed to introduce would allow treatment by day surgery of outpatients, with consequent savings and avoidance of the inconvenience to patients of a stay in hospital. The figures envisaged by experts for developing this activity show the following totals:

<u>Concept</u>	<u>Amount</u>
• Personnel	[12.000.000, 13.000.000, 14.000.000] ptas./year
- Capacity.....	[1.500, 1.700, 1.900] treatment/year
• Property	[15.000.000, 15.300.000, 15.800.000] ptas./year
- Capacity.....	[1.900, 2.100, 2.500] treatment/year
- Length of time	[5'8, 6, 6'2] years
• Lease.....	[2.400.000, 2.800.000, 3.000.000] ptas./year
- Capacity.....	[1200, 1200, 1.200] treatment/year

- Insurances.....[200.000, 225.000, 250.000] ptas/year
- Publicity.....[450.000, 500.000, 550.000] ptas/year
- Miscellaneous supplies.....[200.000, 250.000, 275.000] ptas/year

In addition, each patient treated involves an outlay of [8,000, 9,000, 10,000] pesetas in variable costs. It is also known that the average amount charged by the company for the operation will be [25,000, 30,000, 35,000] pesetas. Further, the experts estimate that market share will not exceed 1,950 cases, not fall below 400, with the most likely outcome being treated of 1,500 cases per year.

In Chart 1, the calculations and data representing the situation as described are given. These shown that the main advantage of the fuzzy threshold of profitability calculated in this way, apart from the ease of expression of the starting data, is the ability of working with all the available information. This remains so even when it is vague or imprecise, and there is no need to let entropy fall by using average values for the options and judgements of experts. It should be pointed out that the results will also be expressed as confidence triplets, which allows a picture more like real life to be given.

It is also possible to draw the following conclusions from Chart 1:

- The number needed to attain the profitability threshold will not be under 654 patients, since below this level fixed costs would not be covered. The number will not exceed 1,387, but the most likely figure is 920 patients. In this way, the decision makers can be aware of all the possibilities in the calculations performed.
- For some levels at which the threshold might at first sight be reached, there are restrictions imposed by the estimated market share or the capacity of productive resources. Thus, it is possible that as many as 1,386 patients would be needed to reach the threshold of profitability, but this is not feasible because of the limitations arising from installed capacity, which is intended to be for 1,200 patients per year. In this case the restriction on capacity arises from the premises. This can be seen from the fact that the productive resources other than premises which put restrictions on the number of patients are fittings and staff, with values of [1,900, 2,100, 2,500] and [1,500, 1,700, 1,900] respectively. NO further calculation is required to see that these are figures greater than those for the premises.

Fixed costs	Personnel	[	12.000.000,	13.000.000,	14.000.000	]
	Property	[	2.419.355,	2.550.000,	2.724.138	]
	Length of time(n)	[	5'8,	6,	6'2	]
	Historic value	[	15.000.000,	15.300.000,	15.800.000	]
	Lease	[	2.400.000,	2.800.000,	3.000.000	]
	Insurances	[	200.000,	225.000,	250.000	]
	Publicity	[	450.000,	500.000,	550.000	]
	Misc. Supplies	[	200.000,	250.000,	275.000	]
Unit variable cost		[	8.000,	9.000,	10.000	]
Sale prix		[	25.000,	30.000,	35.000	]

Market share		[	400,	1.500,	1.950	]
Capacity	Property	[	1.900,	2.100,	2.500	]
	Personnel	[	1.500,	1.700,	1.900	]
	Rent	[	1.200,	1.200,	1.200	]

Summary:

Profitability Threshold:..... [654'42, 920'24, 1.386'61]
Market Share:[400, 1.500, 1.950]
Capacity:[1.200, 1.200, 1.200]

Chart 1

Furthermore, it may be desirable to compare the results derived from this model with those of the model traditionally envisaged in accounting literature. To do so, let the data that would be used in a classic calculation (crisp) for this same instance be taken as being the values of greatest probability used in the example.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has proposed a need to adapt the cost-volume-profit model to situations where the information available is subjective, estimated on the basis of expert judgements, and where past data cannot be extrapolated directly. This can be done by establishing a "fuzzy threshold of profitability" model, allowing the use of imprecise and subjective data for those variables for which it is not feasible to obtain any other type of information. This points to the principal advantage of applying such a model to the making of management decisions, since managers of enterprises are familiar with their environment, and thus know that the

information which they have available and can make use of is diffuse or uncertain. In the light of this it seems obvious as opposed to models which are only in theory exact.

It is thus possible to suggest that the model proposed here would be useful for decisions such as pricing policy, in which models of this sort have not traditionally been considered.

In addition, using this model it is possible to carry out sensitivity studies of the "What would happen if ...?" type. This is its main attraction when it is used as an aid to the taking of decisions affecting the future. For these, it can be seen to have the advantage of working with all the possibilities, and offering a vision of the future situation which, unlike the classic approach, can take into account all points of view.

Likewise, as it is easy to obtain information when it may be as subjective as needed, features such as capacity, market share, and so forth can be included in the calculation and analysis of the threshold of profitability. Despite their strong correlation with the other variables in the model, the classic approach did not take them into account. In this way, the fuzzy model gets as close as possible to reality and always provides a view of all the possible outcomes.

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